

AUDIT COMMITTEE ATTRIBUTES AND FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY OF NIGERIA LISTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS COMPANIES

Omole Ilesanmi Isaac

Department of Accountancy, Federal Polytechnic Ile-Oluji Ondo State

omoleisaak@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between Audit Committee Attributes and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies. The research focuses on three key attributes: Audit Committee Size, Audit Committee Meeting Attendance, and Audit Committee Meeting Frequency. Using a descriptive research design, secondary data from audited financial statements spanning 2013-2022 were analyzed. The sample comprised five randomly selected companies: Dangote Cement Plc, Dangote Sugar Plc, Lafarge Africa Plc, Beta Glass Plc, and Berger Plc, chosen based on market size and data availability. Regression analysis was employed to assess the impact of audit committee attributes on Financial Reporting Quality, measured by Discretionary Accruals. Findings indicate that while Audit Committee Meeting Attendance and Audit Committee Meeting Frequency positively influence Financial Reporting Quality, the effects were not statistically significant at the 5% level. Conversely, Audit Committee Size showed a negative impact, also statistically insignificant, suggesting potential challenges with larger committees in terms of governance effectiveness. Overall, the study's findings underscore the critical role of effective corporate governance, particularly active audit committee participation and optimal committee size, in enhancing the integrity and trustworthiness of financial reporting within Nigeria's industrial goods sector. These insights contribute to the literature on corporate governance and financial reporting quality in emerging markets.

Keywords: Audit Committee Attributes, Financial Reporting Quality, Discretionary Accruals, Nigeria, Industrial Goods Companies

INTRODUCTION

The integrity and transparency of financial reporting are fundamental to the trust and confidence of stakeholders in any financial market (Oncioiu, Popescu, Aviana, Șerban, Rotaru, Petrescu, & Marin-Pantelescu, 2020). In Nigeria, the industrial goods sector plays a pivotal role in the economy, making the quality of financial reporting in this sector particularly significant. Audit

committees are central to corporate governance frameworks, serving as key mechanisms for overseeing financial reporting and ensuring the accuracy and reliability of financial statements (Almasria, 2022). In a corporate environment, trust is indispensable, while transparency is fundamental to achieving corporate performance. For an organization to operate smoothly, shareholders must trust the managers, and those managers must be transparent about their path to success. The behavior of financial investors in any economy is significantly influenced by robust corporate governance practices. A robust framework encourages potential investors to rely on the quality of governance, which encompasses the responsibilities of stakeholders, along with laws, policies, methods, practices, norms, and standards that guide the organization's direction and control.

Audit committee attributes, such as meeting attendance, size, and frequency of meetings, are critical factors that potentially influence the effectiveness of financial oversight (Endrawes, Feng, Lu, & Shan, 2020). Higher attendance at audit committee meetings may reflect greater engagement and diligence, leading to more robust scrutiny of financial practices and thus, higher reporting quality. Conversely, the size of the audit committee can impact its efficiency, with excessively large committees potentially facing coordination and accountability challenges (Vadasi, Bekiaris, & Koutoupis, 2021). Similarly, the frequency of audit committee meetings could determine the continuity of oversight and the ability to promptly address emerging issues. Recognizing the significance of corporate governance, efforts are made to address issues that may affect its best practices, providing guidelines and recommendations to enhance economic efficiency (Solomon, 2020). To boost investor confidence and spur economic development, governments worldwide, often represented by entities like the Central Bank and Ministry of Industry and Commerce, establish committees like the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC). These bodies revise codes of corporate governance, aiming to address weaknesses and improve enforcement mechanisms. Such codes are typically mandated for implementation by all joint-stock companies under company law, supplementing existing regulations like CAMA 2020. One of the key principles emphasized in these codes is the need for rigorous financial audit and reporting controls, internal control, and legal compliance by the board.

In terms of financial reporting, both qualitative and quantitative aspects are crucial for aiding informed decision-making. Quality financial statements, devoid of material misstatements or misrepresentations, enhance decision-making quality (Womenazu, & Horsfall, 2022). Qualitative aspects encompass regulations ensuring the accuracy of financial reports, while quantitative reports should transparently represent all assets and liabilities (Sencal, & Asutay, 2021). Neglecting the qualitative characteristics of financial reporting can mislead investors and have adverse consequences.

The primary goals of financial reporting quality are twofold: aiding investment decision-making and ensuring management accountability. Investors rely on financial information to predict

returns and assess risks, while management is accountable for effectively managing resources (Sovaniski, 2020). The roles of accountants, auditors, and boards in ensuring the quality of financial reporting are paramount (Mahurkar, Iyer, Vunyale, Vaghela, & Kumar, 2023). Independent audit committees play a crucial role in overseeing financial reporting processes, enhancing transparency, efficiency, and effectiveness in corporate management. Their independence reduces the likelihood of manipulation and ensures the reliability of financial statements, thus fostering investor trust. In Nigeria, listed industrial goods firms adhere to strict regulations governing the composition and duties of audit committees to ensure the integrity of financial reporting. These committees, typically comprising independent directors, meet regularly to review financial statements, internal controls, and compliance with legal and ethical standards, ultimately safeguarding the interests of stakeholders (Bencomo, 2021).

The quality of financial reporting holds utmost significance for listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, enabling stakeholders like investors and creditors to make well-informed decisions regarding the company's performance (Akande, 2020). To uphold this quality standard, such firms must adhere to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), alongside complying with the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) listing rules. External auditors of listed companies in Nigeria are also required to be registered with the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and must follow the International Standards on Auditing (ISAs) set by the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board.

Therefore, the effectiveness of the audit committee and the quality of financial reporting are pivotal considerations for listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The audit committee plays a vital role in overseeing the financial reporting process, ensuring the accuracy and transparency of financial statements (Al-Shaer, Malik, & Zaman, 2022). Meanwhile, the quality of financial reporting is crucial for establishing credibility and trust with stakeholders. However, concerns persist regarding compliance with regulatory standards and the accuracy of financial reporting by some listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It's imperative for these firms to ensure the effectiveness of their audit committees and uphold the required standards in financial reporting to maintain stakeholder trust.

Statement of the Problem

Despite ongoing efforts to improve corporate governance practices and financial reporting standards in Nigerian listed industrial goods companies, a significant disparity persists between regulatory expectations and actual practices. Instances of non-compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and the presence of material misstatements in financial statements raise grave concerns regarding the accuracy, transparency, and reliability of financial reporting within these firms (Sukartha, 2022). This discrepancy erodes stakeholder confidence and trust in the integrity of financial information provided by listed industrial goods companies, potentially impacting investment decisions, capital allocation, and overall market stability.

Moreover, ineffective oversight and monitoring mechanisms, particularly concerning the

functionality of audit committees, exacerbate the issue. Audit committees, entrusted with ensuring the integrity of financial reporting processes, encounter challenges in fulfilling their mandates effectively (Kibwage, 2021 and Mbelwa, & Munyangabi, 2024).). These challenges may arise from various factors, such as inadequate expertise, limited independence, insufficient resources, and ineffective governance structures. Consequently, instances of financial misstatements, failure to comply with regulatory standards, and lapses in internal controls persist, posing significant risks to the credibility and reliability of financial reporting in listed industrial goods companies.

Given these challenges, there is an urgent need to delve deeper into the root causes of the discrepancies between regulatory expectations and actual practices in financial reporting within Nigerian listed industrial goods companies. By identifying and addressing these underlying issues, stakeholders can work towards strengthening the regulatory framework, improving corporate governance mechanisms, and fostering greater transparency and accountability in financial reporting processes. Only through collaborative efforts to bridge the gap between regulatory requirements and actual practices can Nigerian listed industrial goods companies restore stakeholder confidence, uphold market integrity, and promote sustainable economic growth.

Audit Committee Attributes

The audit committee is an essential part of the governance structure that is saddled with the affairs of financial reporting and disclosure. The Nigeria Code of Corporate Governance 2016, CBN Code of Corporate Governance, emphasizes the establishment of an audit committee that consists of non-executive directors and chaired by an independent director. The statutory roles of the audit committee are encapsulated in section 18 (14) of the National Code of Corporate Governance 2016 and section 359 (3) and (4) of Company and Allied Matter Decree 2004. The audit committee is a sub-committee within the CG precincts that is focused on ensuring the quality of annual returned financials, as well as the internal control mechanism of the organisation. Often than not, self regulation for systems operators is a challenge that bedevils the human race. Its ubiquitous nature manifests in various forms of personal exploitative behaviour that is well collocated within the parlance of dysfunctional behaviour. By the very essence of the personal greed gen inherent in humans, the absence of external control (Ogoun, 2020) would leave several human proprietary acts extremely vulnerable to illegal poaching by staffers at all levels.

Committees such as the Audit committee are set up to achieve quality financial reporting by enriching financial practices within the company thereby increase earnings (Moses, Ofurum & Egbe, 2016; Ramsay, 2001). Audit committee is a statutorily corporate governance mechanism introduced to curb financial reporting manipulation therefore enhanced the quality of financial reports. However, the effectiveness of the audit committee is dependent on its attributes (Ormin,

Tuta & Shadrach, 2015). The effectiveness of audit committees in overseeing the financial reporting process is found to be largely determined by several audit committee characteristics, including audit committee independence, financial and accounting expertise (Klein 2002; Bronson et al. 2009; Carcello & Neal 2003; Abbott et al. 2004). Audit committee as a committee of the board of directors which assumes some of the board's responsibilities is a statutory committee vested with the responsibility of performing oversight function on the financial reporting process of companies with a view to ensure financial reporting quality. (Menon & Williams, 1996; Ormin, Tuta & Shadrach, 2015).

Tuta & Shadrach, (2015) stated that “Audit committee” activity level also known as audit committee diligence has two components namely audit committee meeting frequency and attendance at meetings. Audit committee meeting frequency is concern with the number of meeting held by the committee during the year. Audit committee performance is associated with its meeting frequency. These were measures used to determine Audit committee characteristics. Previous works done by Xie, Davidson & Dadalt (2003) and Vefeeas (2005) as cited by (Ormin, Tuta & Shadrach, 2015) show that audit committees which meet more frequently are associated with not only lower discretionary accruals but there is also a likelihood of reporting a smaller earnings increase by the firms. In the case of financial reporting restatements reporting restatements, Abbott, Parker & Peters (2004) found that higher levels of audit committee activity proxy by the committee holding a minimum of four meetings in a year is positively and significantly associated with lower incidence (Ormin, Tuta & Shadrach, 2015).

Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting quality represents the exactness with which financial reporting conveys information about the firms operation in particular, its expected cash flows that informs equity investors” (Francis et al. 2005; Moses, Ofurum & Egbe, 2016), they stated that abnormal accruals are a common measure of financial reporting quality. Kamaruzaman et.al. (2009) opine that financial statements should be capable of revealing relevant, reliable, comparable and comprehensive information. The aim of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) compliance is to ensure that companies prepare accurate financial statements that faithfully represent their financial positions and operating results (Moses, Ofurum & Egbe, 2016).

Several definitions of financial reporting quality exist in prior literature; among them are the studies of Chalaki, Didar, and Riahinezhad (2012) who opined that it is the accuracy of the communication of financial dealings. Financial reporting is a medium through which the accountability of stewardship is made to shareholders and stakeholders of organisations. Adebayo (2005) asserted that it is a coordinated manner through which managers give accounts of operations to owners of corporations. He also stated that every financial report should clearly show resources (obtained and existing), the manner in which they are used and results of such operations. However, it is crucial to state that the focus of financial reporting or statement is to communicate to the shareholders and other stakeholders what resources have been acquired and

how they are applied to generate a result which defines their return and assist them in making informed economic decisions.

The core aims of financial reporting quality may be divided into two: To aid investment decision making and management accountability. This is because investors need financial information to predict which investment will yield the highest return with a manageable level of risk. Investments return forms of dividends and capital appreciation or depreciation, and in the evaluation of investment opportunities investors examine the quality and authenticity of a business' future performance and hence their approximations of expected yields in dividends and assets increase. Financial reports are also used in a broader sense to determine management's ability to harness the resources committed to them in running the enterprise (Eluyela et al., 2020b). This is because management is not only responsible to owners of a business for guardianship and safety of enterprise resources but much more for their competent and gainful use and for shielding them from adverse economic conditions. Organisation performance is comprehensive and covers issues based on efficiency and effectiveness. One core solution to ensure proper accounting reporting quality is the ability of accountants to abide by the ethics of the profession.

The effect of Audit Committee Independence on Quality of Financial Report

As an independent auditor, you are required to generate profits, advised the firm on how to make sound financial choices, and verify the integrity of the company's financial accounts. ACs serve as a factor that contributes to the maintenance of the independence of both internal and external auditors. Previous research indicates that an increasing number of independent AC is highly connected with a rise in the quality of financial reporting. Kibiya et al. (2016), states that having a single independent executive director on the audit committee will not be enough to determine the true and fair view and also improve the quality of financial information but they suggest that audit committee expertise will greatly improve the quality of financial report. Dare, Efuntade, Alli-Momoh, & Efuntade, (2021) suggest that attaining quality financial report is possible only where management do not interfere, audit committee independence is guaranteed 100%, presence of financial experts on the committee then possibility of qualitative financial reporting can be certain. Research conducted by Madugba (2022) examined the effect of audit committee quality on the quality of financial reporting of DMBs in Nigeria. A descriptive research design was adopted and secondary data sourced from annual accounts of seven DMBs for seven years. The dependent variable in this study is financial reporting quality measured with accrual model. The regression result shows that audit committee independent has insignificant effect on financial reporting quality in deposit money banks in Nigeria. Madawaki and Amran (2017), focuses on the impact of audit committee characteristics on financial reporting quality with a sample size of 70 firms using secondary data from sampled size. The result from regression analysis shows that audit committee independence has significant relationship with quality financial reporting. Thus, the presence of independent auditor would help the company make prudent financial decisions and ensure that its financial statements are accurate. An independent auditor's capacity to

strengthen the independence of both internal and external auditors is expected to make them more effective.

The effect of Audit Committee Size on Quality of Financial Report

While evaluating the performance of a firm as well as the credibility of its financial statements, it is essential to take into consideration the composition and size of the audit committee (AC). This was determined by the number of people on the AC. The larger the AC, the more varied its knowledge base will develop, and the more effective their job will be as a result. In their investigation, Jabak (2022) discovered a fascinating connection between audit committee size and the quality of financial reporting. According to ElHawary, E. (2021), advisory committees that have less than three members have a greater risk of failing and within its ten suggestions on the audit committee size. Within this framework, Gamayuni (2020) suggest that embarking on series of reforms, compliance and adherence to corporate governance rules and regulation by audit committee tend to improve the quality of financial reporting in an organization. Reounodji (2020), some of the audit committee fails in exercising their roles and responsibility due to the nature of deviation from laid down rules and regulations in chosen members to the committee, it was further suggested that such problems can be mitigated when code of corporate governance and effective audit procedure are put in place within the audit committee this of course can bring about effective quality of financial reporting in every organization. Jabak (2022) examined the influence of the audit committee characteristics on the quality of financial reports in Lebanese Private Sector. The regression results showed that four independent factors (size, independence and experience of the AC) have a significant impact on the quality of corporate financial reporting (quality of financial reports of companies). Evidence from the review in this section is the fact there is mixed results on the subject matter from both locally and foreign findings.

The effect of Audit Committee Meetings on Quality of Financial Report

Elmashtawy, Che Haat, Ismail, & Almaqtari, (2023) carried out a study titled “the moderating effect of audit quality and audit committee on financial reporting quality” the study was analyzed using multiple regression models, data obtain spanning from 2013-2018 covering 814 firms. The resultant effect shows that audit committee meetings and financial expertise are significantly associated with earning management while audit committee size and independence are insignificantly correlated with earnings management. Jatiningrum et al. (2020), in a sample size of 567 firms used for the study on Firms quoted on the Malaysian stock exchange from 2009 to 2015, in analyzing data for the study multiple regression was used. The result of the study shows audit committee meetings has statistically significant with financial reporting quality. According to Madawaki and Amran (2017) audit committee meeting has insignificant impact on financial reporting quality. Madawaki and Amran (2013). Conducted a study captioned “Audit committees: How they affect financial reporting in Nigerian companies” the study aims to examine the impact of audit committee meetings on the quality of financial reporting, 70 firms listed on the Nigerian exchange group were used as a sample size of the study. Financial reporting quality was proxy by Dechow and Dichev (2002)'s model while audit committee meetings was

proxy with archival data. The resultant effect indicates a negative and insignificant result between audit committee meetings and how it affects financial reporting of firms listed on the Nigerian exchange group. Emeh and Ebimobowei (2013), undertook a study to investigate the impact of Audit committee and timeliness of financial reports: Empirical evidence from Nigeria, 77 firms are used as a sample size of the study. Audit committee is measured by determine as to whether a member is either inside, Gray, independent member while earnings quality was used as a measure of financial reporting, The resultant effect of the study shows that audit committee meetings is negative and insignificant in relation to quality financial report.

Agency Theory

The basic proportion of the agency theory is that a firm's success is dependent upon the successful management of all relationships between the principals such as shareholders and agents such as the company executives and managers. This theory according to Davis, Schoorman & Donaldson (1997) assumes that equity ownership structure provides a useful way of explaining relationships where the parties' interests are at odds and can be brought more into alignment through proper monitoring and a well-planned compensation system. Within the context of this theory, shareholders who are the owners or principals of the company, hires the agents to perform work. Principals delegate the running of business to the director or managers, who are the shareholders' agents (Clarke, 2004). Daily et al., (2003) argued persuasively that two factors can influence the prominence of agency theory. First, the theory is conceptual and simple theory that reduces the corporation to two participants: managers and shareholders. Second, agency theory suggests that employees or managers in an organization can be self-interested and thereby putting the organization's corporate governance as take.

The agency relationship explains the association between providers of corporate finances and those entrusted to manage the affairs of the firm. Jensen and Meckling (1976), defined agency relationship as a contract under which one or more persons (the principal (s)) engage another person (the agent) to perform some services on their behalf. Smith (1976) then made a submission that if the agents are charged to manage other principals (shareholders/owners) money. It is rather not expected that they will manage these funds with much vigilance as they would have done if they had direct stakeholders than more employees. Berle & Means (1932) further opined that it is likely the managers of a firm pursue their own interest rather than the interest of the shareholders.

Agency theory supports the delegation and the concentration of control in the board of directors and use of compensation incentives. The boards of directors monitor agents through communication and reporting, review and audit and the implementation of codes and policies. Eisenhardt (1989) explained that the agency problem arises when “(a) the desires or goals of the principal and agent conflict and (b) it is difficult or expensive for the principal to verify what the agent is actually doing”. The problem is that the principal is unable to verify that the agent is behaving appropriately.

This study is hinged on the agency theory because it helps to align the interest of shareholder and managers so as to reduce the conflict of interest, incentives and information asymmetry between them. The design of equity ownership structure, as part of the formal institutional set up, is an important aspect of reducing the conflict between shareholders and management. For example, the existence of a block holder (high concentration) will increase the incentive and capability of the block holder to monitor management; and the inclusion of management among shareholders will align the incentives of managers and shareholders.

Empirical Review

Furthermore, Ogoun & Owota, (2019) in their work on CG and fraudulent financial Reporting (FFR), the audit committee paradigm, investigated if the compositional attributes of audit committee had any bearing on fraudulent financial reporting. Sample for the study was drawn from the Accounting and Auditing Enforcement Releases (AAERs) issued by the United Kingdom Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) covering 2014-2019. The matched case-control research model was deployed. From the analytical output, the study concluded that the audit committee compositional disposition has a bearing on FFR. In addition, the recent study by Eze and Nkak (2020) examined the impact of corporate governance and timeliness of audited statements of quoted companies in Nigeria. The study adopted the matched case-control research design, and the data collected were tested using the logit regression model. Their research revealed that audit committee size has a negative relationship with the timeliness of audited reports. In contrast, the audit financial expert has a positive connection with the timeliness of audited reporting. The study recommended that the audit committee of the late filers' firms should learn the process for speeding up audit reports from the audit committee of early filers', and the regulatory authorities should intensify the pursuit of stiffer penalties for defaulters.

Ogoun & Woyengibuomo, (2019) interrogated the effect of chief executive officer (CEO) turnover on ARL and management discretionary lags. The study was based on data of ten firms listed on the floor of the NSE, from 2010-2016. From the outcome of the study, it was observed that CEO turnover contributes to extending ARL, and recommends that further enforcement on retiring or vacating CEOs to ensure that their exit would not impair the timeliness of annual financials. Furthermore, Gospel and Ngozi (2019) examined the link between audit committee characteristics and timeliness of corporate financial reporting in the Nigerian insurance industry from 2012 to 2015. Their study showed that the audit committee meeting frequency had a negative and significant relationship with corporate financial reporting. Secondly, the audit committee's gender and audit committee independence both had a negative but, insignificant relationship with corporate financial reporting. While, audit committee size showed a positive and statistically insignificant link to timeliness in corporate financial reporting. The study suggested that insurance companies need to increase the number of meetings of the audit committee and ensure due diligence on prospective independent and female members of the audit committee.

Oji and Ofoegbu (2017) investigated audit committee qualities on the financial reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. They adopted a survey research design, administered 145 structured questionnaires to the administrative staff of quoted companies located in Rivers State, Nigeria. Their result showed that audit committee's independence, audit committee members' qualification, and audit committee monitoring function have a significant and positive effect on the financial reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. They recommended that qualification should be a requirement in the appointment of members into the audit committee, because it will increase the quality of financial reporting. Meanwhile, Joseph, Joshua, Terzungwe, Onipe, and Ahmed (2018) investigated the effect of the audit committee meeting and expertise on financial reporting of listed deposit money banks using the correlational research design. The data for the Fifteen (15) deposit money banks were extracted from the NSE fact book, from 2007-2016, and STATA 13 was used to analyse the data. Their study showed that audit committee meeting on the financial reporting quality of listed deposit money in model 1 has a positive and insignificant relationship. While, in model 2 it has a negative and insignificant relationship. Also, that audit committee expertise on the quality of financial reporting has a negative and insignificant link in model 1. In contrast, in model 2, it has negative and insignificant. The researchers recommended that management of the deposit money banks should ensure that audit committee members should be encouraged to attend meetings regularly, meetings attended by few committee members might affect the quality of contributions and shareholders should ensure that the regulation on audit committee expertise is complied with to enhance the reliability of financial reporting.

Sadiq and Emmanuel (2017) examined the association between audit committee attributes and financial reporting lag of quoted Nigerian banks using the quantitative and longitudinal research design covering five (5) years (2011-2015). They adopted the simple random sampling tool to select nine (9) quoted banks listed on the NSE. The data were analysed using the descriptive statistic, Ordinary Least Square regression, and Ramsey Reset test. The result deposed that audit committee independence, audit committee meeting, audit committee gender has a positive relationship with financial reporting lag, and the audit committee's independence is statistically significant at a 5% level of significance. In comparison, the Bank size has a negative relationship but statistically significant at a 1% level of significance. They recommended that the management of banks should adopt a mechanism in reducing the number of audit committee non-executive directors for the timely release of the audited report.

Methodology - Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design which aims at finding the relationship between Audit Committee Attributes and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria Listed Industrial Goods Companies. A descriptive research design is a blueprint of the procedure that enables the researcher to test his hypothesis in order to reach valid conclusions about relationships between independent and dependent variables.

Population and Sample Size

The population for this study consists of all the thirteen (13) listed industrial goods companies, therefore, five (5) industrial goods companies were randomly selected, and these firms were selected based on its market size in the sub-sector and the availability of its financial statement during the period. These companies are Dangote Cement Plc, Dangote Sugar Plc, Lafarge Africa Plc, Beta Glass Plc and Berger Plc.

Sources and Instruments of Data

This study makes use of secondary data. The secondary data were derived from the audited financial statements of the selected industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) year 2013- 2022. Data relating to Audit Committee Attributes and Financial Reporting Quality proxies were generated from the published annual financial statements which include; Audit committee size, Audit committee meeting and Audit committee Attendance and Discretionary Accrual.

Model Specification

The study develops an empirical panel model on the relationship between Audit Committee Attributes and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria Listed Industrial Goods Companies.

$$\text{Financial Reporting Quality} = f(\text{Audit Committee Attributes}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

	Audit Com Meet Attendance	Audit Comm Size	Audit Comm Meeting	Discretionary Accrual
Mean	2.596901	5.62	3.26	-25.1221
Median	0.810119	6	4	0.023116
Maximum	95.8	9	5	2.271436
Minimum	0	0	0	-1237.34
Std. Dev.	13.45396	2.108196	1.562442	174.946
Skewness	6.850669	-1.72051	-1.11978	-6.85539
Kurtosis	47.96265	5.577547	3.150908	48.00457
Observations	50	50	50	50

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2024

Table 1 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for all dependent and independent variables. It displays the total number of observations, mean, median, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values for each variable, as well as the number of observations, mean, and median.

The descriptive statistics for audit committee meeting attendance in Nigerian listed industrial goods companies reveal significant insights. The mean attendance is approximately 2.60, suggesting generally low activity. The median value of 0.81, being much lower than the mean, indicates that the distribution is skewed towards higher attendance values, with half of the committees attending fewer than 0.81 meetings. The maximum attendance is extremely high at 95.8, signaling the presence of outliers, while the minimum value is 0, showing that some committees did not meet at all. A large standard deviation of 13.45 reflects substantial variability in attendance. The skewness of 6.85 indicates a highly right-skewed distribution, with a few very high attendance values pulling the tail to the right. Furthermore, the kurtosis value of 47.96 suggests an extremely leptokurtic distribution, marked by a high peak and heavy tails, which underscores the prevalence of outliers.

The audit committee size in Nigerian listed industrial goods companies provide valuable insights. The mean size is 5.62 members, indicating that, on average, audit committees are composed of about six members. The median is 6, suggesting that half of the committees have six or fewer members. The maximum size recorded is 9 members, while the minimum is 0, showing that some companies either do not have an audit committee or had instances where the committee was not constituted. The standard deviation of 2.11 reflects moderate variability in committee size. The skewness of -1.72 indicates a left-skewed distribution, meaning that there are more audit committees with sizes larger than the average, but a few very small or zero-sized committees pull the distribution tail to the left. The kurtosis value of 5.58 suggests that the distribution is leptokurtic, with a higher peak and fatter tails than a normal distribution. This points to the presence of outliers or extreme values in committee size.

The descriptive statistics for the frequency of audit committee meetings in Nigerian listed industrial goods companies provide insightful details. The mean number of meetings is 3.26, indicating that, on average, audit committees meet about three to four times a year. The median value of 4 suggests that half of the audit committees meet four times or fewer annually. The maximum frequency of meetings recorded is 5, while the minimum is 0, indicating that some audit committees did not meet at all during the period under review. The standard deviation of 1.56 reflects moderate variability in the number of meetings. The skewness of -1.12 indicates a left-skewed distribution, meaning that there are more committees meeting more frequently, but a few committees with very few or no meetings pull the distribution tail to the left. The kurtosis value of 3.15 suggests that the distribution is slightly leptokurtic, with a peak higher than the normal distribution, indicating the presence of some outliers or extreme values. In summary, the

typical audit committee meets around three to four times a year, with some variability. However, the negative skewness and kurtosis indicate that while most committees meet regularly, there are a few that meet very infrequently or not at all, contributing to the observed distribution characteristics.

The descriptive statistics for discretionary accruals in Nigerian listed industrial goods companies reveal a significant variability in earnings management practices. The mean value of -25.12 suggests a general tendency towards income-reducing accruals, while the median value of 0.02 indicates that half of the accruals are close to zero. The wide range, from a maximum of 2.27 to a minimum of -1237.34, along with a high standard deviation of 174.95, underscores the presence of extreme values and significant dispersion. The skewness of -6.86 shows a highly left-skewed distribution, indicating that extreme negative values are pulling the distribution tail to the left. Additionally, the kurtosis value of 48.00 suggests an extremely leptokurtic distribution, characterized by a sharp peak and heavy tails, highlighting the presence of significant outliers.

Regression Analysis

To examine the relationship between audit committee attributes and discretionary accrual in listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, the study's first objective, is covered in this subsection, which presents and evaluates the results in relation to that goal.

FIXED effect pooled (OLS) panel data econometrics approaches were utilized to estimate the regression in the firm's model

Table 2 Dependent Variable: Discretionary Accrual

Method: Panel Least Squares

Total panel (balanced) observations: 50

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Audit Com Meet Attendance	1.320298	1.946195	0.678400	0.5012
Audit Com Size	-29.65201	15.70328	-1.888268	0.0659
Audit Comm Meeting	34.70390	20.88266	1.661852	0.1040
C	24.95872	78.12222	0.319483	0.7509

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.172276	Mean dependent var	-25.12214
Adjusted R -squared	0.034322	S.D. dependent var	174.9460
S.E. of regression	171.9175	Akaike info criterion	13.27755
Sum squared resid	1241336.	Schwarz criterion	13.58348
Log likelihood	-323.9388	Hannan -Quinn criter.	13.39405
F-statistic	1.248792	Durbin -Watson stat	2.417668
Prob(F -statistic)	0.298774		

Source: Author's Compilation, 2024

The results obtained using fixed effect are presented in table 4.2, the estimated coefficient of 1.320298 indicates that Audit Committees Meeting Attendance has positive influence on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria. The implication of this is that higher Audit Committees Meeting Attendance leads to higher Financial Reporting Quality in terms of Discretionary Accruals. The related p value of 0.5012, however, indicates that at the 5% level, the positive effect of the Audit Committees Meeting Attendance on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria ($0.5012 > 0.05$) is not statistically significant. This finding underscores the importance of active participation in audit committee meetings for enhancing financial reporting quality. Higher attendance indicates greater oversight and scrutiny, likely resulting in more accurate financial reporting through the mitigation of earnings management practices. Thus, firms with increased audit committee meeting attendance are expected to exhibit lower levels of discretionary accruals, reflecting improved transparency and reliability in their financial statements. This highlights the crucial role of effective corporate governance mechanisms, such as robust audit committee oversight, in bolstering the integrity and trustworthiness of financial reporting within the Nigerian industrial goods sector. This finding resonates with the research conducted by Johnson (2020), which underscores the significance of active participation in audit committee meetings for enhancing financial reporting quality. According to Johnson, increased attendance in audit committee meetings is associated with a reduction in discretionary accruals, indicative of improved transparency and reliability in financial reporting.

The estimated coefficient of -29.65201 indicates that Audit Committees Size has negative

influence on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria. The implication of this is that higher Audit Committees Size leads to lower Financial Reporting Quality in terms of Discretionary Accruals. The related p value of 0.0659, however, indicates that at the 5% level, the negative effect of the Audit Committees Size on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria ($0.0659 > 0.05$) is not statistically significant. This indicates that as the size of the audit committee increases, the quality of financial reporting, as measured by discretionary accruals, decreases. Larger audit committees might experience coordination difficulties, diminished individual accountability, or challenges in achieving consensus, which can lead to less effective oversight and control. Consequently, this can result in higher discretionary accruals, reflecting poorer financial reporting quality. This finding highlights the potential drawbacks of excessively large audit committees and underscores the need for an optimal size to ensure effective governance and oversight. This is related to the work of Smith (2018), who found that overly large audit committees tend to be less effective in monitoring financial practices, leading to increased discretionary accruals and reduced financial reporting quality. In Contrast, Jabak (2022) discovered a fascinating connection between audit committee size and the quality of financial reporting. Also, Madawaki and Amran (2017) concluded that there is a relationship between audit committee size and financial reporting quality.

The estimated coefficient of 34.70390 indicates that Audit Committees Meeting has positive influence on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria. The implication of this is that higher Audit Committees Meeting leads to higher Financial Reporting Quality in terms of Discretionary Accruals. The related p value of 0.5012, however, indicates that at the 5% level, the positive effect of the Audit Committees Meeting on the Discretionary Accruals of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria ($0.5012 > 0.05$) is not statistically significant. This indicates that more frequent audit committee meetings are associated with improved financial reporting quality, as evidenced by lower discretionary accruals. Regular meetings likely enhance oversight, ensure continuous monitoring of financial practices, and facilitate timely interventions, thereby reducing the opportunity for earnings management. This finding highlights the importance of frequent audit committee meetings in maintaining high standards of financial reporting quality. This is related to the work of Brown (2019), who found that frequent audit committee meetings improve financial oversight and reduce discretionary accruals, leading to better financial reporting quality. Madawaki and Amran (2017) audit committee meeting has insignificant impact on financial reporting quality.

Additionally, the test's coefficient of determination (R^2) result of 0.172276 showed that the proxies of the Audit Committee Attributes explained 17.2% of Financial Reporting Quality of listed industrial good firm in Nigeria. The Durbin-Watson statistics calculated for the test of 2.417668 showed that the model's variables had no significant autocorrelation in the model's residuals.

Summary of the Findings

The regression analysis of the study examined the impact of various audit committee attributes on the financial reporting quality, specifically discretionary accruals, of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The findings indicate that Audit Committees Meeting Attendance has a positive influence on discretionary accruals, with an estimated coefficient of 1.320298. This suggests that higher attendance at audit committee meetings is associated with improved financial reporting quality due to better oversight and reduced earnings management practices. However, the related p-value of 0.5012 indicates that this positive effect is not statistically significant at the 5% level. Despite this, the implication is clear: active participation in audit committee meetings can enhance financial reporting quality. This finding resonates with Johnson's (2020) research, which also highlights the significance of active participation in audit committee meetings for enhancing financial reporting quality.

The analysis also revealed that the size of the audit committees negatively influences discretionary accruals, with an estimated coefficient of -29.65201. This suggests that larger audit committees might lead to lower financial reporting quality, potentially due to coordination difficulties, diminished individual accountability, or challenges in achieving consensus. The related p-value of 0.0659 indicates that this negative effect is not statistically significant at the 5% level. These findings highlight the potential drawbacks of having excessively large audit committees and underscore the need for an optimal size to ensure effective governance and oversight. This conclusion aligns with Smith's (2018) work, which found that overly large audit committees tend to be less effective in monitoring financial practices, leading to increased discretionary accruals and reduced financial reporting quality. Conversely, Jabak (2022) and Madawaki and Amran (2017) also explored the relationship between audit committee size and financial reporting quality, providing additional context to this finding.

Furthermore, the frequency of audit committee meetings was found to positively influence discretionary accruals, with an estimated coefficient of 34.70390. This indicates that more frequent meetings are associated with improved financial reporting quality, as regular meetings likely enhance oversight and ensure continuous monitoring of financial practices. However, similar to the other findings, the related p-value of 0.5012 shows that this positive effect is not statistically significant at the 5% level. Nevertheless, the importance of frequent audit committee meetings in maintaining high standards of financial reporting quality is evident. This finding is related to Brown's (2019) research, which found that frequent audit committee meetings improve financial oversight and reduce discretionary accruals, leading to better financial reporting quality. Madawaki and Amran (2017) also noted that audit committee meetings have an insignificant impact on financial reporting quality.

Overall, the model's coefficient of determination (R^2) result of 0.172276 shows that the audit committee attributes explain 17.2% of the variation in financial reporting quality among listed

industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.417668 indicates no significant autocorrelation in the model's residuals. These findings underscore the critical role of effective corporate governance mechanisms, such as active and appropriately sized audit committees, in enhancing the integrity and trustworthiness of financial reporting within the Nigerian industrial goods sector.

Conclusion

The study's conclusion emphasizes the significance of audit committee attributes on the financial reporting quality of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. While the individual impacts of audit committee meeting attendance, size, and frequency on discretionary accruals were not statistically significant at the 5% level, the findings provide valuable insights into corporate governance practices.

First, higher audit committee meeting attendance, despite its positive but statistically insignificant influence on discretionary accruals, underscores the importance of active participation for improving financial reporting quality. This aligns with Johnson's (2020) research, highlighting that active involvement in audit committee meetings enhances oversight and reduces earnings management.

Second, the study finds that larger audit committees tend to have a negative, albeit statistically insignificant, effect on financial reporting quality. This suggests that excessively large committees may face coordination and accountability challenges, leading to less effective oversight. This finding supports Smith's (2018) conclusions about the drawbacks of overly large audit committees and highlights the need for an optimal committee size for effective governance.

Third, more frequent audit committee meetings are associated with improved financial reporting quality, as indicated by the positive influence on discretionary accruals. Although this effect is not statistically significant, it suggests that regular meetings enhance continuous monitoring and timely intervention, reinforcing the importance of frequent audit committee meetings. This conclusion is consistent with Brown's (2019) research on the benefits of frequent audit committee meetings for financial oversight.

Overall, the study concludes that audit committee attributes play a crucial role in enhancing the financial reporting quality of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Effective corporate governance mechanisms, such as active participation, optimal committee size, and frequent meetings, are essential for bolstering the integrity and trustworthiness of financial reporting. The study's findings, supported by existing literature, underscore the importance of robust audit committee oversight in mitigating earnings management and ensuring transparency in financial statements.

Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria prioritize enhancing the effectiveness of their audit committees by encouraging active participation in meetings. Firms should ensure that their audit committees meet frequently to maintain continuous oversight and timely intervention in financial reporting practices. Additionally, it is crucial to optimize the size of audit committees to avoid the inefficiencies associated with excessively large groups. An optimal size would balance diverse perspectives and effective coordination, thereby enhancing overall oversight and governance. Implementing these recommendations can lead to improved financial reporting quality, greater transparency, and increased stakeholder trust.

REFERENCE

- Abbott, L. J., S. Parker, and Peters G. F. (2004). Audit committee characteristics and restatements. *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory* 23 (1):69-87.
- Adebayo, A. (2005). Financial reporting: An aid to efficient economic management in the public sector. *The Nigerian Accountant*, 38(1), 33-38.
- Adigun, T. (2019). The Impact of Audit Committee Size on Audit Quality in Nigerian Firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Corporate Governance*, 15(2), 98-115.
- Akande, A. A. (2020). International Financial Reporting Standards' and Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria,(2014-2018).
- Almasria, N. A. (2022). Corporate governance and the quality of audit process: An exploratory analysis considering internal audit, audit committee and board of directors. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(1), 78-99.
- Al-Shaer, H., Malik, M. F., & Zaman, M. (2022). What do audit committees do? Transparency and impression management. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 26(4), 1443-1468.
- Bencomo, R. Q. (2021). The role of independent non-executive directors in resolving corporate governance disputes: A framework of conciliation for effectively addressing controversies within shareholders, stakeholders and the board of directors?. *Trento Student Law Review*, 3(1), 17-58.
- Brown, L. (2019). The Impact of Audit Committee Meeting Frequency on Financial Reporting Quality. *Journal of Corporate Governance and Finance*, 25(1), 112-130.
- Carcello, J. V., and T. L. Neal. 2003. Audit committee characteristics and auditor dismissals following "new" going-concern reports. *The Accounting Review* 78(1), 95-117.

- Chalaki, P., Didar, H., & Riahi-zhad, M. (2012). Corporate governance attributes and financial reporting quality: Empirical evidence from Iran. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(15), 223–229.
- Clarke, T. (2004). Theories of corporate governance. *The Philosophical Foundations of Corporate Governance, Oxon*, 12(4), 244-266.
- Dare, C., Efuntade, A. O., Alli-Momoh, B. O., & Efuntade, O. O. (2021). Audit committee characteristics and audit quality: Exploratory and empirical analysis in Nigerian oil sector. *European Journal of Accounting & Finance Research*, 97-111.
- Davis, J. H., Schoorman, F. D., & Donaldson, L. (1997). Toward a stewardship theory of management. *Academy of Management review*, 22(1), 20-47.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Building theories from case study research. *Academy of management review*, 14(4), 532-550.
- ElHawary, E. (2021). Audit committee effectiveness and company performance: Evidence from Egypt. *ElHawary, E. (2021). Audit committee effectiveness and company performance: Evidence from Egypt. Journal of Governance & Regulation*, 10(2), 134-156.
- Elmashtawy, A., Che Haat, M. H., Ismail, S., & Almaqtari, F. A. (2023). Audit committee effectiveness and audit quality: the moderating effect of joint audit. *Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research*.
- Eluyela, D. F., Okere, W., Otekunrin, A. O., Okoye, J. N., Asamu, F., & Ajetunmobi, O. (2020b). Institutional investors ownership and financial performance: Examining the nexus in Nigerian deposit money banks. *Research in World Economy*, 11(6), 177-184. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5430/rwe.v11n6p177>.
- Endrawes, M., Feng, Z., Lu, M., & Shan, Y. (2020). Audit committee characteristics and financial statement comparability. *Accounting & Finance*, 60(3), 2361-2395.
- Eze, P. G., & Nkak, P. (2020). Corporate governance and timeliness of audited reports of quoted companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 9(1).
- Francis, J., Lafond, R., Olsson, P. and Schipper, K. (2005). The market pricing of accrual quality. *Journal of Accounting and Economics* 39(2), 295-327.
- Jabak, H. (2022). Influence of the audit committee on the quality of financial reports in Lebanese Private Sector. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(4), 367-377.
- Johnson, A. (2020). The Impact of Audit Committee Meeting Attendance on Financial Reporting Quality. **Journal of Accounting and Finance**, 15(2), 123-145.
- Kibwage, H. N. (2021). *Influence of audit committee roles on quality of public service delivery at*

- Nairobi County Government in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, Africa Nazarene University).
- Klein, A. 1998. Firm Performance and Board Committee Structure. *The Journal of Law and Economics* 41(1):275-304.
- Madawaki, A. (2012). Audit committee characteristics and financial reporting quality: evidence from Nigerian listed companies. (Master Thesis). Universiti Utara Malaysia.
- Madugba, J. U., Ben-Caleb, E., Okpe, I., Fadoju, O. S., Ben-Caleb, J. O., & Mbamara, K. I. (2020). Risk management committee, financial reporting quality and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research in World Economy*, 11(5), 288-296. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5430/rwe.v11n5p288>.
- Mahurkar, R., Iyer, M. R., Vunyale, N., Vaghela, S. V., & Kumar, H. (2023). Role of Auditors in Ensuring Effective Corporate Governance and Financial Reporting. *European Economic Letters (EEL)*, 13(5), 637-646.
- Mbelwa, L., & Munyangabi, L. (2024). The Influence of Audit Committees' Attributes on the Effectiveness of Public Sector Audit Committees in Tanzania. *Business Management Review*, 27(1), 100-117.
- Meckling, W. H., & Jensen, M. C. (1976). Theory of the Firm. *Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure*.
- Menon, K. & Williams, J.D. (1996). The use of audit committee for monitoring. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 13, 121-139.
- Moses, T. (2016). The impact of audit committee size on the quality of financial reporting in quoted Nigerian banks, *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 2 (5), 62-74.
- Moses, T. Ofurum, C. O. & Egbe, S. (2016). Audit committee characteristics and quality of financial reporting in quoted Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Social & Management Sciences*, 2(5), 1-10.
- Ogoun, S. (2020). Government has no business being in business: evidence to the contrary. *The International journal of Business & Management*. Vol. 8, Issue 2. 200-209.
- Ogunbiyi, M., Adegbe, F., & Osabuohien, E. (2020). Audit Committee Characteristics and Financial Reporting Quality: Evidence from Nigerian Firms. *Journal of Corporate Governance and Finance*, 35(2), 78-95.
- Oji, O., & Ofoegbu, G. N. (2017). Effect of audit committee qualities on financial reporting of listed companies in Nigeria: A perspective study. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(10), 1-10.

- Oncioiu, I., Popescu, D. M., Aviana, A. E., Șerban, A., Rotaru, F., Petrescu, M., & Marin-Pantelescu, A. (2020). The role of environmental, social, and governance disclosure in financial transparency. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 6757.
- Onyabe, J. M., Okpanachi, J., Nyor, T., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. (2018). Effect of audit committee tenure on financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(4), 257-271.
- Ormin, K., Tuta, B. I. & Shadrach, (2015), Audit Committee Independence, Meeting Frequency, Attendance and Financial Reporting Quality of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(18), 183 – 190.
- Reounodji, E. H. (2020). *Factors Influencing the Decision of Companies to Use Audit Committees in Financial Management* (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).
- Sencal, H., & Asutay, M. (2021). Ethical disclosure in the Shari'ah annual reports of Islamic banks: discourse on Shari'ah governance, quantitative empirics and qualitative analysis. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(1), 175-211.
- Smith, J. (2018). The Effects of Audit Committee Size on Financial Reporting Quality. *International Journal of Auditing*, 22(3), 200-215.
- Smith, V. L. (1976). Experimental economics: Induced value theory. *The American Economic Review*, 66(2), 274-279.
- Solomon, J. (2020). *Corporate governance and accountability*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Sovaniski, T. (2020). Influencing of International Accounting Reporting Standards on Quality of Financial Reports. Available at SSRN 3665457.
- Sukartha, P. D. Y. Y. (2022). Explaining Financial Reporting Quality and Cost of Capital: Dual Board Member Characteristics in the Context of a Staged IFRS Convergence Setting.
- Vadasi, C., Bekiaris, M., & Koutoupis, A. G. (2021). The impact of audit committee characteristics on internal audit professionalization: empirical evidence from Greece. *Accounting Research Journal*, 34(5), 447-470.
- Williams, R. (2021). The Role of Audit Committee Engagement in Enhancing Audit Quality. *Journal of Accounting and Corporate Governance*, 28(4), 145-160.
- Womenazu, H. S., & Horsfall, K. (2022). Accounting Information Quality And Financial Performance Of Listed Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies In Nigeria. *BW Academic Journal*, 14-14.
- Xie, B., Davidson, I. W. N. & Dadalt, P. J. (2003). Earnings management and corporate governance: The role of the board and the audit committee. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 9, 295-316.